

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

NATIONAL MENTALITY AND ITS FEATURES

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Abstract

The differences between nations are due to their different historical destinies. In the modern world, it is necessary to realize the interrelationship of various national interests, since the national mentality permeates all spheres of society: culture, politics, science, everyday life, family, economy, etc. The mentality is based on a deep awareness of each person's belonging to their national community, which has its own traditions and customs, communication manners and ethical norms.

The history of each nation, as is well known, experiences a wide variety of turning points in its development, and it is precisely such events that determine the state of the national mentality that characterizes the character of the people. The greatness of a people is determined not by their age, but by the level of spirituality they have achieved and their specific contribution to human civilization. Some politicians inspire their people and openly declare to the whole world in the information space about the greatness and antiquity of their people and claim what never belonged to them, thereby acquiring a distinctive feature of their mentality. The mentality is brought up and absorbed by the people themselves, usually based on concrete positive examples, therefore the every people constantly take care of improving and enriching their spirituality.

Keywords: mentality, ethics, spirituality, historical memory, ethnic roots, the Azerbaijani people.

The topic that we are exploring about mentality and the specifics of mentality, in the context of community and differences among peoples, is very relevant. In the culture of every nation, there is always something universal, universal and, at the same time, specific, national and special, that unites people of an ethnic group. The differences between nations are due to their different historical destinies. A great contribution to the research of the mentality of peoples was made by the development of genetics, which made it possible to trace the history of entire peoples in the footsteps of individual fragments of the human genome.

The term "mentalities" was introduced into scientific use by the French ethnologist and socio-anthropologist L. Levy-Bruhl. The philosophical understanding of the concept of "mentalities" is associated with the name of the German thinker E. Cassirer, who put into the concept of "mentality" about the same content as L. Levy-Bruhl, emphasizing that types of mentalities can be systematized according to the ways of perceiving the world around them. The mentality has a contradictory nature and embodies the dual opposition of innovation and tradition. Both sides of the dual opposition of the mentality of innovation and tradition are necessary, and there must be a balance between them, a kind of balance.

In the modern world, it is necessary to realize the interrelationship of various national interests, since the national mentality permeates all spheres of society: culture, politics, science, everyday life, family, economy, etc. Throughout their history, nations have accumulated solid experience in nonviolent conflict resolution. The resolution of problems related to ethnic conflicts, clashes based on national hostility and a way out of these problems is possible with a consistent state policy. It should be emphasized that people of different nationalities can quite get along with each other if one nation does not put itself above the other and if it develops

immunity to various harmful attempts to influence the minds of the younger generation by various nationalist movements.

The mentality of peoples also reflects a set of value orientations, the ability to feel and act in accordance with national interests. Absolutely opposite features can be found in each of the peoples, because the root of the character of a particular people grows from the subconscious of people. The mentality is based on a deep awareness of each person's belonging to their national community, identification with this community. Addressing the topic of mentality is one of the ways that deserves scientific analysis.

Basically, mentality is reflected in the actions of people, their way of thinking, which leaves its mark in folklore, literature, and the art of nations. Scientific and artistic literature, for example, of the Azerbaijani people, whose authors were the ancestors of today's Azerbaijanis, such as the philosopher Bahmanyar Al-Azerbaijani of the XI century, the philosopher and poet Nizami Ganjavi of the XII century, the philosopher and poet Nasimi of the XIV century and others, provides great information for studying the mentality of the Azerbaijani people. Although many representatives of Azerbaijani culture and science wrote in Farsi, Arabic, and Russian, depending on which conqueror the Azerbaijani people were, nevertheless, the specificity of the Azerbaijani mentality, which is based on its ancient Turkic language, has always been traced. The peculiarities of the historical fate of the Azerbaijani people, the economic, socio-political and cultural environment had a great influence on the formation of their mentality. The national mentality of the Azerbaijani people has its own peculiarities, since the root of mentality was formed in ancient times on the basis of Avestan teachings and Zoroastrianism, and much has been preserved in the mental character of the Azerbaijanis, but over time, coming under the influence of various conquerors

(Persians, Arabs, Russians), some changes occurred, as the conqueror imposed his state language, and even religion, as it was during the Arab conquest in the sixth century. The 30-year struggle of the ancestors of the Azerbaijanis, led by Zoroastrian Babek, against the Arab conquerors who taxed those who did not accept the new religion, nevertheless led to the fact that, having preserved their ancient traditions, the ancestors of the Azerbaijanis converted to Islam, embodying in their mentality the main goal - to be spiritual and believe in the power of the Almighty God. In Zoroastrianism, there has always been a five-time prayer (from sunrise until dark), and therefore the ancestors of the Azerbaijanis also continued all their traditions, performing ablutions, necessarily wearing belts, which were removed only during prayer and sleep, and performing worship five times a day to this day, only doing it in Arabic in the Islamic version. By the way, there are belts in Azerbaijani national clothes, but with the advent of Soviet power and the Europeanization of clothing, belts have disappeared, although in the wedding ceremony, before the wedding, the bride is always tied with a red belt in a wedding dress, which is a symbol of the strong figure and stability of the creator of a new family.

However, it should also be noted that prior to the Arab invasion, and even earlier, Alexander the Great, a conqueror seeking to enrich Greek culture, desired to not only appropriate the wealth of these lands but also incorporate their cultural achievements. He ordered the destruction of the Avesta and the execution of Zoroastrian clerics (magicians, commonly known as mugs). Despite the prohibitions imposed by Arab and other invaders, the observance of Novruz, a spring festival, and numerous other ancient customs, which remain the holiest traditions for Azerbaijanis since Zoroastrian times, has been preserved to the present day. Even when Azerbaijan was a part of the Soviet Union and the celebration of Novruz was prohibited by the Communist atheistic ideology as an archaic practice, the tradition remained deeply ingrained in the collective consciousness of Azerbaijanis, causing every family to continue to observe the holiday in secret, despite official condemnation.

Currently, there is a growing interest and desire among individuals and entire nations to preserve their ethnic heritage. This desire for identity preservation has become one of the primary factors leading to the dissolution of the Soviet Union, as it represents the pursuit of national independence.

Mentality, on the other hand, is a means by which individuals can identify with their social group and form social solidarity. It is based on a sense of belonging to a particular community, which is further enhanced by awareness of one's role within that community. The formation of this sense of social identity is influenced by both genetic factors and the natural and social environments in which an individual lives.

Mentality expresses its archetypal content through culture. It is defined by a cultural code, which is primarily carried by the intelligentsia.

The concept of "archetype" was introduced by Carl Gustav Jung in 1919, in his article "Instinct and the Unconscious". Jung sought to identify the units of influence that shape and determine the behaviors and

experiences of humanity as a whole, as well as individuals. Jung defined the archetype as the unconscious content that becomes conscious and perceptible, undergoing changes under the influence of individual consciousness. Although mentality is generally conservative, it does change over time through people's experiences. Archetypes, meanwhile, were "imprinted" in the human psyche during the formation of humanity and are passed down unchanged from generation to generation. He believed that in order to gain a comprehensive understanding of the mental characteristics of a people, it is essential to examine their history, cultural background, significant traditions, customs and rituals [1, p. 274].

The mental disposition of individuals is closely intertwined with the societal underpinnings of the community, traditions and practices that form an integral part of the lives of those who belong to it. Typically, national customs have a strong and enduring presence in society, naturally permeating human consciousness. The perception that has been shaped may differ from that formed by representatives of another cultural background, yet there are unique aspects due to historical heritage. The mental makeup of each people is a persistent characteristic passed down to each new generation, with a historically prevalent emphasis on collectivism.

If we look at the historical process as a whole, then all the changes in the history of any nation had a long preparation in the sphere of the spirit of these peoples. Each new epoch gave rise to new spiritual values, which are guided by the public consciousness of the peoples. Each nation has its own face, its own culture, its own traditions, which hides its essence. Human behavior is mainly determined by norms, patterns, and values. Currently, there is a need for identification due to communication and information processes, and therefore some peoples want to distinguish their "I". Another thing is how they do it, for example, some nations want to show their superiority over other nations, and some do not need to advertise the mental achievements of their people, since there is no such trait in the national character to praise themselves.

Each state is home to representatives of not just one, but several ethnic groups, and therefore a fusion of cultures occurs, with the dominant ethnic group playing a dominant role. The language of each people is one of the essential characteristics of the ethnic group, an important component of its history and culture. Although peoples share many common words, each has developed its own language. Mentality is the result of birth, upbringing, indoctrination, and conscious persuasion, through which a person determines their ethnicity. In the history of the Azerbaijani people, the state language was most often the language of the country that enslaved them. Therefore, Azerbaijani poets, writers, and scholars wrote in Farsi, Arabic, and Russian (under Soviet rule), but works in Azerbaijani survive, such as those by Nasimi (14th century) and others.

Spiritual culture is of great importance for nations, which permeates all aspects of social interaction between people, creating a sense of unity. The mentality of a society, even of one nation, is heterogeneous. The spiritual elite develops higher culture on the basis of mass culture. Later, by introducing the meanings of

higher culture into the mass consciousness through the intelligentsia, it enriches the mass mentality, which becomes capable of striving to maintain the establishment of more progressive social relations. This is the interaction of the mentality of the spiritual elite and the mentality of the masses.

The spiritual world regulates the activity (communication, behavior, activity) of the subject as a whole, and the mentality within the spiritual world determines the specific nature of this activity. Ethnic mentality is the most important component of ethnic consciousness. Images and attitudes specific to each ethnic group, behaviors and attitudes towards the world, nature, man, his "ethnic group" and other peoples ("we" and "they"). Since these features in the culture of an ethnic group pass from generation to generation, they turn into fairly stable traditions, they become stable stereotypes of people's thinking and behavior. The process of formation of an ethnic mentality is continuously connected with the general process of becoming a person, forming him as a personality. According to the behavior and actions of a person as a person, one can judge her spiritual and moral qualities (both positive and negative).

The mentality of the people and the historical memory of the people have common and distinctive characteristics. Historical memory is a system-forming element of public consciousness with its inherent mechanism of imprinting, storing, reproducing socio-cultural information and represented as a system of traditions, customs, etc. passed down from generation to generation. Mentality and historical memory reflect a generalized national and cultural peculiarity of the people. They carry collective principles, and reproduce from generation to generation all the accumulated experience of mankind. Mentality and historical memory are the main indicator of the integrity and unity of the entire nation.

The memory of the people preserves the knowledge that a person acquires in his individual experience, makes it possible to use them expediently when one generation is replaced by another. History, as you know, is experiencing a wide variety of turning points in its development. The life of any nation takes place in close interaction with this diverse, mysterious world. In the current scientific, technical and information space, any people cannot unequivocally assert that their self-sufficient life is provided only at home, without direct invisible outside interference.

If the mentality of a people is in constant humiliation and dependence, but lives by a lofty idea based on the true history of their people, then they achieve freedom and development for their people. And in extreme situations, the national spirit turns into a kind of magical magic force, since the spirit of the people rises when it represents a single integrity. For example, starting in the 90s of the twentieth century, for 30 years, the Republic of Azerbaijan tried to peacefully return part of the Azerbaijani lands seized by Armenian extremists, but since the world community was informed in the information space by fakes about the "antiquity of the Armenian people", etc., therefore, it was difficult for Azerbaijanis to receive support from any country. Officially, no country has recognized the lands of Azerbaijan occupied by Armenian extremists, as according to

documents and in fact, the ancestors of Azerbaijanis have always lived on these lands. And when it was not possible to return their lands through years of peaceful negotiations, then the Azerbaijani people united and, under the guidance of the wise policy of their President Ilham Aliyev, were able to defeat the Armenian aggressor. Currently, the Azerbaijani people are building houses and restoring all the systems that were destroyed by the Armenian aggressors over 30 years. Azerbaijani families who were driven out by armed means then will now be able to return to their liberated homelands of Azerbaijan. The mentality of an individual cannot be separated from the mentality of his people. A man cannot be indifferent to the troubles of his people. E. Fromm tried to comprehend the nature of the national mentality, its connection with the characteristics of socio-cultural existence in his works. Through the disclosure of the social potential of a national character, he explained many of the social transformations taking place in society [2, p.178].

People have a sense of national pride. But the mentality of different nations understands national pride in different ways. The antiquity of a people is not the main criterion of its greatness and sanctity. Although the Azerbaijani people have been formed on the ancestral lands of Azerbaijan since the Zoroastrian times, and have benevolence and hospitality in their national character, they never brag about it, as Armenian politicians do in the Internet information space. The greatness of a people is determined not by their age, but by the level of spirituality they have achieved and their specific contribution to human civilization. Any nation can admire its ancient and distinctive culture, but the level of civilization is determined by the current level of development of society. Armenian politicians inspire their people and the whole world in the information space about the greatness and antiquity of their people, and also cause self-pity by claiming that there was an alleged genocide of Armenians in Ottoman Turkey in 1915, which in fact did not happen, and this fairy tale was invented only in 1962 by the special services of the Soviet Union, in order to use against Turkey.

Every nation should develop comprehensively economically, scientifically, and spiritually. In order to raise the spirit of the people, it is necessary to recognize their very essence with the true story of their people, and not an invented one. The spirit is nurtured and absorbed by the people themselves, at least by their absolute majority, and with concrete positive examples. The people who have a healthy spirit will always achieve the best results for development. The spirit rises when the blessed self-sufficient life of the people is ensured, when people look to their future with honor and faith. The national spirit is organically woven into the fabric of state power and valor.

In the historical past, different nations had glorious pages. They are associated with the achievements of material and spiritual culture, which aroused and still arouse the admiration of many nations. The historical path of each nation is the emergence and establishment of national traditions and customs, the attitude to which is ambiguous. In the mentality of many nations, there is a good tradition of hospitality, a glorious tradition of

helping other nations in trouble. In particular, the Azerbaijani people are famous all over the world for their hospitality, as anyone who has ever visited Azerbaijan, where people of many nationalities live together, can confirm. The Azerbaijani people also showed their hospitality when, in the early 19th century, after several Azerbaijani khanates fell under the rule of tsarist Russia and several other khanates came under the rule of Iran (after the Russian-Iranian war), a large number of people of Armenian nationality were resettled from Iran and Ottoman Turkey to the lands where Azerbaijanis lived, to increase the number of people of the Christian religion. They were literally attached to all Azerbaijanis, and from there came Armenian surnames with Azerbaijani names and words ending in *yang*, which means “near” whom they live or “what they do”. And then the local Azerbaijanis treated the Armenian settlers who arrived with understanding, helped them with food, clothes, and gave them the opportunity to earn money, since the Russian Empire paid them each only a small amount of money for a short time. But in the future, these Armenian settlers and their descendants, at turning points in history, tried to appropriate the lands of Azerbaijanis, taking advantage of the opportunities. This was the case after the Socialist Revolution, for example, in 1918, gangs of Armenian terrorists killed hundreds of civilians of various nationalities in several cities of Azerbaijan, and this was the case during the collapse of the USSR in the 90s of the twentieth century. And nowadays, in the information space of the Internet, it is easy to meet the fantasies of Armenian politicians that their country should stretch “from sea to sea” and that they are “the most ancient people in the world”.

Modern Azerbaijan is a multinational country, having received a rich heritage from generation to generation, enriched its mentality with spirituality and knowledge that lead to progress. The mentality of Azerbaijanis, combining spirituality with Islamic flavor and ancient traditions from the Zoroastrian times (celebrating Novruz), has a tolerant character in its national way of life. The mentality of the Azerbaijani people has al-

ways been in favor of cultural synthesis, because Azerbaijan has historically been at the crossroads of various world cultures.

In every country, the mentality of every nation has traditions and customs of communication and ethics. Love for loved ones, pain at their loss, are a universal human trait and do not turn out to be something specific for some and absent from other communities. The universal human principle usually overcomes the inertia of traditions anchored in the mentality.

The mentality ensures the connection of times and the continuity of generations. Mentality is transmitted mainly through the mechanisms of mass consciousness and ensures the unity of the spiritual sphere in its development, and therefore the new generation in the process of socialization perceives the mentality of their society. G. Shpet in his work “Introduction to Ethnic Psychology” concluded that the key to understanding the mentality of a people lies in its history, in the specific structure of social reality, embodying the “collective spirit of the nation” [3, p. 190].

The mentality of each nation is unique in its own way, and it can be said that there are no “bad” and “good” nations, since there are sane people in every nation who can lead their people on the right path. Currently, against the background of global processes in the world, it is important to correctly identify the mental characteristics of each nation in order to avoid possible interethnic clashes and conflicts. For this, there is a need for a comprehensive study of the national mentality: it is especially important to scientifically predict how a particular mental property may determine the behavior of a people or its individual representatives in a particular cultural and historical situation.

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